

RELEVANCE OF VEDIC TEXTS AS A SOURCE OF VALUES AND CULTURE IN CONTEMPORARY EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Literary meaning of values can broadly be identified as moral principles that control or influence a person's behavior or a system of moral principles or rules of behavior/ principles which affect a person's behavior in a positive sense. The Indian subcontinent is the one of the oldest civilizations of the world which was well aware of improving the quality of life through these means and has significantly emphasized on these very normative principles of moral conduct. NEP 2020 has also placed great importance on inculcation of values through education at various levels. This paper remains a humble attempt at exploring ancient Indian texts as a source of timeless values and culture that remain relevant in the modern education system. The study principally focusses on the Upanishads in tandem with other ancient Indian texts as a valuable source of values much needed for a balanced synchronized modern society.

Keywords: Ancient India, Values, Culture, Relevance, Education

INTRODUCTION

Literary meaning of values can broadly be identified as moral principles that control or influence a person's behavior or a system of moral principles or rules of behavior/ principles which affect a person's behavior in a positive sense. These principles have a great, definite and undoubtedly a great deal of direct influence on a normal human behaviour. This refers to the mental faculty which enables a man to probe, distinguish and choose from the good and bad in positive sense which comes to a person with inward concentration.

NEP 2020 and Perception of Value Education

In alignment with the goals of NEP 2020, the NEP places equal importance on value education which includes moral values, Indian values and universal values like:

- **Ethical values:** NEP 2020 seeks to cultivate in students ethical values such as empathy, respect, integrity, and responsibility, and recommends their infusion in the curriculum, co-curricular activities and assessments.
- **Traditional Indian values:** As per the NEP 2020, core traditional Indian values such as ahimsa, swachchhata, satya, nishkam karma, shanti and sacrifice should be included in the education tasks.
- **Basic human values:** In the same vein the NEP 2020 acknowledges importance of certain basic human values such as tolerance, diversity, pluralism, righteous conduct, gender sensitivity etc in education.

- **Curriculum:** The broad aim of NEP 2020 is to redefine the curriculum framework to one that is contextually Indian and local. It is expected of the curriculum to help shape the students into responsible individuals imbued with the values of regularity, punctuality, and self-control.
- **Teachers' training:** Similarly, the NEP 2020 intends to empower teacher training institutions and programs in order to support incorporation of ethical values.

The Indian subcontinent is the one of the oldest civilizations of the world which was well aware of improving the quality of life through these means and they have much been talked about through Indian poetry, drama, prose and fictions. The entire ancient Indian literature, in one way or the other way, have significantly emphasized on these very normative principles of moral conduct. Values eventually lead to a realization of life as a journey of self-emancipation or the process of becoming from being. An individual, who is on the path of self-realization and who has to achieve his objective yet, is a bundle of imperfections and only through these means of moral corrections, he can achieve the final destination. Therefore, it is a process of becoming from being or coming to the real existence. This very process of becoming is revealed through moral up-righteousness on which all of the Upanishads have categorically emphasized upon to a great extent. The Upanishads not only emphasize on the ultimate reality that is the final destination of human life but also provide the substantial guidelines and code of conduct for the seeker who is on this very path of self-realization.

OBJECTIVES

The research paper has the following objectives:

- i. To explore the normative principles of moral conduct embedded in the ancient Indian Vedic and Upanishadic texts
- ii. To study the modalities of self-realization suggested by the Vedic and Upanishadic literature.
- iii. To explore how values and morality are perceived as optimal ways of self-liberation and a peaceful existence in the ancient Indian Literature
- iv. To investigate how ethics are perceived as integrated into personal and social life in the ancient Indian texts
- v. To enquire how mental equanimity achieved through systematic mediation and control of senses have been suggested by the ancient Indian texts as an essential virtue and value necessary for a healthy and meaningful life.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This paper has a qualitative research approach that is aligned with historical inquiry, focusing on descriptive and analytical methodologies to provide a nuanced view of ethics, morality and values, in tandem with modalities of attaining the same as suggested by the ancient Indian texts. Both primary and secondary sources have been used. External criticism (authenticity verification) is done to assess the reliability of the sources used, while internal criticism (interpretative analysis) has been done for a critical examination of the content, biases, and

underlying assumptions within these texts. The approach employed is essentially descriptive-analytical, aiming to reconstruct and interpret contributions of the Vedic and Upanishadic texts to the understanding and conceptualization of personal and social value systems and the assessment of the same as a mode of attaining a meaningful healthy life.

ANALYSIS

The Upanishads and values

The ethics of Upanishads can be divided in to two major categories, namely

- **Social Ethics:** Ethics of Upanishads which contribute towards the stability of the healthy human society. It includes the qualities such as sense of Unity, negation of malpractices etc.
 - **Personal Ethics:** Ethics of Upanishads which contribute to the onlooker in the spiritual progression in the life such as longing for goodness in life, negation of escapism, penance, chastity, compassion, truthfulness etc.
- a. **Social Ethics:** The *Ishavasya Upanishad* makes a distinctive and clarion call for synergy, unity and harmonious co-existence. It urges all the people, disputing with each other over a small piece of land, to give up every type of niggardliness and consider the whole of the earth as the abode of the Lord. It is proclaimed when the Supreme Being prevails in every biotic and abiotic manifested form, it is a trivial matter of no importance to quarrel over the transient material gains. The *Ishavasya Upanishad* asks the human beings to renounce the selfishness or the meanness by which the future of this world may be changed :
- i. *îûâvâsyamida Asarvam* [All this, whatsoever moves on earth, is enveloped by the Lord,” establishes the fundamental principle of divine immanence. It suggests that the divine is not separate from the world but is inherent in it.]
 - ii. *yastusarvâ Gibhûtâniâtmanyevânupaúyati, sarvabhûtecucâtmânaA* [He who sees all beings in the Self and the Self in all beings, ceases to hate”. This highlights the core teaching of recognizing the unity of all beings through the Self.]
 - iii. *agnenayasupathârâyeasmânviúvâni deva vayunânividvân yuyodhyasmajjuhurâ GamenobhûyicmhâCte nama uktiCvidhema* [O *Agni*, lead us by the good path to the enjoyment of the fruits of our deeds, knowing O God, all our deeds. Remove the sin of deceit from within us. We offer thee many prostrations by word of mouth].
- b. Again, the Shantipatha or the prayers made in the beginning of all of the Upanishads denote the longing for the peace “serenity that yields the understanding to all”, thereby reflecting a profound emphasis on peace, harmony and synergy as innate values of cardinal significance. The *KathaUpanishad*, again, indicates the sense of oneness at common platform but also, on the contrary, shows the selective sense of sharing which enables the person to transcend the unworthy ideas of meanness and self-domination. The *IshaUpanishad* on the other hand, tries to concentrate on the concept of cosmic unity through proclamationslike “ One, who sees all beings in self and self in all beings,

he never hates anyone at all". Needless to say that the idea of hate emerges in a situation when one does not consider himself as a part of a comprehensive community in positive sense and separates or individualizes himself from the other on the basis of selfishness, greed, lust and other unworthy ideas. But as one considers and realizes the other beings as his own integral part, in such a case, whole of the picture takes turns topsy-turvy in positive sense and presents itself in a different perspective.

The *Aitareya Upanishad* begins with the one Spirit creating the universe out of its being. As guardians for the worlds, Spirit made the Purusha (person). Out of the cosmic egg came speech, breath, eyes and sight, ears and hearing, skin, hair, and herbs; from the navel and outbreath came death, and from the organ of pleasure seed and waters were born. In the last chapter of this Upanishad the it is asked who is this Spirit by whom one sees and hears and smells and speaks and knows? The answer is the following:

That which is heart, this mind—that is, consciousness, perception, discernment, intelligence, wisdom, insight, persistence, thought, thoughtfulness, impulse, memory, conception, purpose, life, desire, will are all names of intelligence.

This intelligence comes close the supreme consciousness that permeates all beings. All things are guided by and based on this intelligence of Spirit (Brahman). Ascending from this world with the intelligent soul one obtains all desires in the heavenly world even immortality.

The *Chandogya Upanishad* denounces unethical social practices and warns the entire society not to make mistakes. The *Chandogya Upanishad* emphasizes ethical conduct through the concept of interconnectedness and the importance of self-realization. It highlights the principle of non-harm (ahimsa) and the recognition that all beings share the same essence (Atman), which is ultimately Brahman. Treating all with love and compassion, understanding the unity of existence, and striving for self-knowledge are core ethical principles are suggested as essential values :

- a) rayodharmaskandhâyajño' dhyayana Adânamitiprathamastapaevaditîyobrahma câryâcâryakulavâsît [tîyo'tyantamâtmanâmâcâryakule' vasâdayansarvaetepu Gyalokâbhavantibrahmasastho'm[tatvameti]] [There are three divisions of dharma: Sacrifice, study and charity form the first. Austerity is the second. Dwelling in the house of the teacher as a brahmacharin, always mortifying the body in the house of the teacher, is the third. All those who practise these dharmas attain the worlds of the virtuous. But one who is established in Brahman obtains Immortality.]
- b) yo ha vaijyeshthamchshreshthamchvedjyeshthasch ha vaishre [When a man knows the best and the greatest, he becomes the best and the greatest.]
- c) o vaiuttamamveda, uttamabhavati/Yovaisthiramveda, sthirabhavati/Yovai siddhi veda, siddhi bhavati/o vaig[hamveda, g[hambhavatipara% [He who knows excellence, becomes excellent/He who knows stability, becomes stable/He who knows success, becomes successful/He who knows home ,becomes home for others.]

Thus, moral guidelines provided by the Upanishadic literature not only set guard the human society against all odd practices but on the contrary to it asks the society to be aware of such damaging vices which are avoidable and are not demanded in a healthy society.

Vedic scriptures, particularly the *Rigveda* and *Atharvaveda*, emphasize values like truth, compassion, and self-awareness. The importance of selfless action, living in harmony with nature, and recognizing the divine within oneself and all beings is repeatedly highlighted in these two Vedas. The *Brihadaranyaka Upanishad* asserts: “Sarva parabasangdukkhangsar vama tmbasang” or One should, perform karma with nonchalance without expecting the benefits because sooner or later one shall definitely get the fruits. This is a value asserted in the *Bhagbad Gita* as well. The *Manusmriti* reiterates that highlights a core concept in Indian philosophy: the idea that true happiness and well-being are found within oneself, while relying on external factors or other people for happiness leads to suffering. It emphasizes the importance of self-reliance and inner peace as a path to liberation from suffering :

“sarvamparavasamdukhkamsarvamatmavasamsukhametadvidyatsama senalaksa nam sukhaduhkhayoh”.

Self-reliance and peace emerges through the value of selflessness and lack of greed. The *Brihadaranyaka Upanishads*, chapter IV, documents a conversation between Yajnavalkya and Maitreyi where the inanity of material wealth and mindless pursuit of the same has been denounced in favour of the virtue of a synchronized pursuit of inner knowledge of self-realization and self-emancipation:

“ 2.4.2 Thereupon Maitreyi said: “Venerable Sir, if indeed the whole earth, full of wealth, belonged to me, would I be immortal through that?” “No,” replied Yajnavalkya, “your life would be just like that of people who have plenty. Of Immortality, however, there is no hope through wealth.” 2.4.3 Then Maitreyi said: “What should I do with that which would not make me immortal? Tell me, venerable Sir, of that alone which you know to be the only means of attaining Immortality.” [...] “Verily, not for the sake of wealth, my dear, is wealth loved, but it is loved for the sake of the self. “Verily, not for the sake of the brahmin, my dear, is the brahmin loved, but he is loved for the sake of the self [...] “Verily, not for the sake of the gods, my dear, are the gods loved, but they are loved for the sake of the self. “Verily, not for the sake of the beings, my dear, are the beings loved, but they are loved for the sake of the self. “Verily, not for the sake of the All, my dear, is the All loved, but it is loved for the sake of the self. “Verily, my dear Maitreyi, it is the Self that should be realized-should be heard of, reflected on and meditated upon. By the realization of the Self, my dear-through hearing, reflection and meditation-all this is known.”

Self-realization implies the realization of the oneness of the inner consciousness with the Supreme consciousness after which all manifested forms are perceived as reflections of the one and only Absolute Being. This paves the way to eradication of discrimination, violence and vices of hatred and envy:

Verse 2.4.12 – “As a lump of salt dropped into water becomes dissolved in water and cannot be taken out again, but wherever we taste the water it tastes salt, even so, my dear,

this great, endless, infinite Reality is Pure Intelligence alone. This self comes out as a separate entity from these elements and with their destruction this separate existence also is destroyed. After attaining oneness, it has no more consciousness [...]” For when there is duality, as it were, then one smells another, one sees another, one hears another, one speaks to another, one thinks of another, one knows another. But when everything has become the Self, then what should one smell and through what, what should one see and through what, what should one hear and through what, what should one speak and through what, what should one think and through what, what should one know and through what? Through what should One know That owing to which all this is known-through what, my dear, should one know the Knower?”

c. Personal Ethics: It is said that one who has realized his true inner self is the genuinely ethical person. Thus, as far as the achievement of the self-realization is concerned, the entire Upanishadic literature provides the necessary guidelines for the onlooker. Dr. Radhakrishnan, in his book titled *Indian Philosophy* speculates that “In one sense, Upanishadic morality is individualistic for its aim is self-realization.” Again, the Kena Upanishad repeatedly emphasizes life’s greatest virtues like chastity, desire-less action, faith etc. as profound personal values by rendering various stories to the one who is on the path of self-realization. The *Katha Upanishad*, surprisingly is very conscious about the spiritual progression of every one when it proclaims suggestively “Arise, awake and get the final objectives and realize them.” The ancient Indian texts are resonant with references that reveal that the process of self-realization is a process of becoming from being in which one has to uplift himself by means of these very basic qualities of human life for self-liberation and this only can be done by means of adopting the greatest virtues of human life. The *Kathopnishad* asserts that the human mind encounters relentless and confounds to choose from the good, better, best and pleasant and *Kathopnishad*, very subtly, has presented the discrimination in this regard by proclaiming the idea that “The better is one thing, the pleasant may be other. Both of these, having different aims, bind the person.” And at the same time, subtle difference is also made clear through proclamation “These both, come to man’s will. The wise person makes the discrimination after judging both of them and opts for the best for him and the fool chooses the reverse.” Almost all of the Upanishads like *Katha*, *Kena*, *Ishavasya*, *Chaandogya* etc. repeatedly stress upon the life’s greatest virtues as selfless service and lack of lust as is the pre-requisite for everyone who are on the path of self-liberation. The *Ishavasya Upanishad* categorically asserts in this regard -” Yearn for not the wealth of anyone at all.” Again, we find an illuminating conversation between Yama and Nachiketa in *Kathopnishad* where the lord of death Yama tells Nachiketa that man can never be satisfied with wealth no matter how vast that is. The Upanishads repeatedly direct the entire humanity, irrespective of caste or creed, to be aware of the innumerable hazards present in the path of self-liberation and provides a set of innate personal yet universal values that would serve as a beacon of light in the shrouding darkness of temptations, perplexities and conflict.

The Upanishads clearly put forth the idea of not giving up one’s life in order to escape from performing actions. Escapism is treated as a vice and thus ancient Indian texts set a premium upon taking responsibility and negotiating oddities of life with integrity and honesty.

The *Ishavasya Upanishad* argues that Satanic are these worlds that celebrate escapism and with blinding darkness are they covered. One who puts forth his prayer for selfish gains and comfort, falls prey to this darkness and warns all men that it is sinful to develop the tendency of escapism. On the contrary, one may wish to live a full life while performing the sensible actions, guided by both personal and social values. Dedicated honest work is important. The *Brihadaranyaka Upanishads* clearly assert that “just like one acts, accordingly one conducts himself, so does he become. One becomes virtuous by performing worthy and virtuous deed and other becomes evil by performing the unworthy deeds.” The Upanishad does not restrict itself here only but goes one step further by arguing that human willpower is omnipotent and a man made of desires engages in deeds born out of his own deep-seated desires. Hence it is obvious that a person desirous of attaining the spiritual growth, would naturally perform the right and just actions always and would get the best results accordingly. Thus, values are considered to be integral to human character, in the form of purity of thoughts and intention and not a simple mechanical code of conduct.

Virtues related to meditation and asceticism (tapas)—self-control, tranquillity, self-denial or renunciation (nysa), desirelessness, fasting also figure in the list of values reflected by the *Taittereya Upanishads I.9*, *Brihadarakanya Upanishads (Book IV, verse 4.6-7, 4.22, Book VI.2.16)*, *Chhandogya Upanishad II.23*, and *Kena Upanishad (Book IV, 8)*. Two moral virtues are repeatedly highlighted as important, namely, truthfulness (satya-vachana). The closest the Upanishads come to suggesting that morality is required on the path to liberation from rebirth is in the *Katha Upanishad*, where it is asserted that the self is not grasped by a man who has not quit misbehaviour (dushcharitra), is not tranquil, and is without a stilled mind (Book II. Verse 24). In the medieval *Mahabharata*, the term “dushcarita” means bad or wrong behaviour or wickedness and refers to what is considered the chief forms of misbehaviour, namely, murder, theft, lying, covetousness, envy, and so forth. The action-guide is given in the context of personal cultivation and does not suggest an other-regarding concern. That is, we need to cease committing selfish acts in order to make progress towards attainment of knowledge of brahman and such a change in conduct would orient us away from self-centeredness and towards the reality underlying everything. Self-control, not external control, remains the centre of concern.

Control of anger is also seen as a virtue that needs to be mastered as a value. The *Naradaparivrajaka Upanishad* highlights “akrodha”, meaning non-anger, as essential for self-knowledge and liberation. It emphasizes enduring harsh words and treating everyone with respect, even those who are angry. The Upanishads teach that controlling anger is a significant aspect of self-control, which in turn is crucial for controlling the mind and preventing harmful actions. Swami Budhananda (1917-1983) of the Ramakrishna Mission, noted in a series of talks on anger published in *Vedanta Kesari*: “The evil effects of anger are innumerable. The first thing that happens to an angry person is that he forgets the lessons of wisdom he has learnt in life. After that, he loses control over his thoughts and emotions. He becomes overactive, with his highly charged ego as his only guide. He loses his power of discrimination, sense of proportion, and becomes aggressive in manner, hostile to his own welfare. When anger becomes the second nature of a person, physical health and equanimity of mind suffer, and inner peace

vanishes in a trice. Anger can destroy friendships, families, business partnerships, professional prospects. Communal and ethnic riots, arsons, wars, suicides, murder and many other forms of crime are basically products of anger. In fact, anger makes even a handsome person look ugly. I suggested to a friend, who is remorseful about his flashes of anger, that he keep a large mirror facing his office desk. In case the anger-prone person has a lively sense of humor, this mirror-therapy is likely to work.”

DISCUSSION

The enlightened state is a spiritual state and is the supreme value and goal of self-development. Value-systems, like all cultural phenomena, have a rich history and the ancient the Upanishads provide an insight into the cultural perception of self-emancipation as a prolonged austere journey towards enlightenment that constitutes value system of our society. The modern society rift with mindless materialism, pursuit of personal comfort and a deeply confused perception of life as a mindless accumulatio of material wealth and instant sense gratification seems to resemble a radar less boat in a tumultuous ocean as evident from the ever escalating cases of depression, self-harm, violence in variegated forms and a deep-seated lack of joy and satisfaction. The Upanishadic and ancient Indian cultural echoes of innate values could perhaps provide an understanding of the journey of life and provide direction to an otherwise lost wayfarer. A well-planned and systematic integration of ancient Indian wisdom into the modern curriculum emerges as the need of the hour as material success and gains have evidently failed to provide peace, contentment and succour to the struggling generations blinded by alien cultural invasions and deviations from their own roots.

REFERENCES

- Gambhirananda, Swami (1982). *Eight Upanishads*, Calcutta, Advaita Ashrama.
- Roebuck, V. (2004). *The Upanisads*, Penguin; Rev ed. Edition.
- Sternbach, L. (eds.) *Maha-Subhasita-Samgraha: The Most Comprehensive Collection of Sanskrit Quotations Ever in Eight Volumes*. https://archive.org/details/Mahaasubhaasitasamgraha_Vol_1/page/n5/mode/2up
- Puligandla, R. (1975). *Fundamentals of Indian Philosophy*. Abingdon Press.
- Ministry of Human Resource Development. 2020. *National education policy 2020*. New Delhi: Government of India.
- Nath, R. C. (1982). *The New Hindu Movement*. Minerva.
- Radhakrishnan, S. (2006). *Principal Upanishads*. Harper Collins.
- Prabhananda, S. & Manchester, F. (2002). *Breath of the Eternal Upanishads: the Wisdom of the Hindu Mystics*. Penguin.
- Jananlokananda, S (2023). *Mulyobodhen Dhonyo Jibon*. Printcare.